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EFFECTIVENESS OF PSYCHOMOTOR THERAPY FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM: RESEARCH RESULTS

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ANNOTATION

This article highlights the improvement of the quality of life of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder through psychomotor therapy, the correct application of skills in practice, and the results of these investigations.

Keywords: Psychomotor therapy, ASD, defects

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АУТИЗМ СПЕКТРИ БОР БОЛАЛАРГА ПСИХОМОТОР ТЕРАПИЯНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. ТЕКШИРУВЛАР
НАТИЖАСИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада Аутизм спектри бор болаларнинг ҳаёт тарзини психомор терапия орқали яхшилаш, кўникмаларни амалиётда тўғри қўллаш ва шу текширувлар натижаси ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Психомотор терапия, аутизм, дефектлар

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПСИХОМОТОРНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ ДЕТЯМ С АУТИЗМОМ. РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещаются улучшение качества жизни детей с расстройством аутистического спектра с помощью психомоторной терапии, правильное применение навыков на практике и результаты этих исследований."

Ключевые слова: Психомоторная терапия, аутизм, дефекты.

Introduction.

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is recognized globally as a significant public health issue characterized by deficits in social communication, stereotyped interests, and repetitive behaviors. The fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) classifies ASD as a neurodevelopmental disorder. In recent decades, the prevalence of ASD has dramatically increased worldwide, with an average rate of 62 per 10,000 children. Given the early onset of the disorder, its complex impact, including psychiatric comorbidities, and the lack of a current cure, early intervention programs are crucial. ASD significantly affects not only the lives of individuals diagnosed but also those of their families and caregivers. Thus, early diagnosis and strict management can greatly enhance rehabilitative outcomes for children with ASD.

ASD's primary characteristics, such as persistent deficits in social communication and interaction across multiple contexts, and restricted, repetitive patterns of behavior, interests, or activities, can vary in severity and may be compounded by additional medical issues,

including epilepsy, sleep disorders, gastrointestinal problems, cognitive impairments, and maladaptive behaviors like hyperactivity, anxiety, irritability, self-harm, and aggression. Effective treatment for children with ASD requires a multidisciplinary approach combining educational interventions, behavioral therapies, speech and language therapy, occupational therapy, and medical treatments (e.g., psychopharmacology).

The complexity of ASD, which involves medical, psychological, social, educational, and ethical dimensions, necessitates a careful balance of different diagnostic and rehabilitative approaches. Despite various proposed treatment strategies, no consensus on a single best approach has been reached. Psychomotor treatment, widely used in Europe, is one such approach, also known in other countries as psychomotor or play therapy. In Uzbekistan, similar methods are gradually being introduced for ASD therapy.

The psychomotor approach focuses on children's development through movement during play sessions, aiming to enhance social signals (eye contact, smiling, etc.), increase attention span, encourage

communication, and improve object use. Play holds significant therapeutic value in this context, naturally fostering cognitive development in children with ASD.

This therapy supports and strengthens the child's functional areas of development and requires a comprehensive approach tailored to each child's unique needs. Psychomotor intervention addresses these diverse needs through a highly individualized approach, supporting the child's spontaneous actions and play in various forms. Furthermore, psychomotricity is considered a safe and effective therapy for many neurodevelopmental disorders.

To date, evidence on the efficacy and feasibility of psychomotor therapy for children with ASD in Uzbekistan remains limited. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of six months of psychomotor treatment on children with ASD and its potential impact on various aspects of their lives.

Materials and Methods.

We recruited 60 children from Tashkent and surrounding regions of Uzbekistan, diagnosed with level 3 ASD according to DSM-5 criteria, aged between two and nine years. The study was conducted between December 2023 and June 2024. Participants were selected through convenience sampling from rehabilitation centers in Tashkent and nearby regions. Data were collected anonymously following parental informed consent. Inclusion criteria were: (a) a level 3 ASD diagnosis per DSM-5, confirmed through the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule, Second Edition (ADOS 2, module 1) for children and the Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revised (ADI-R) administered to parents by qualified psychologists; (b) participation in psychomotor therapy during the observation period; (c) age between two and nine years; and (d) absence of comorbid psychiatric or neurological conditions.

Given that the patients were diagnosed in different clinics and the extensive training required for ADOS-2, the Childhood Autism Rating Scale (CARS 2) was also used to enhance ASD diagnosis in clinical practice. This reliable tool is specifically designed to identify ASD in children from two years old. The test includes fifteen items related to key behavior areas, scored from 1 to 4. The total score ranges are: (1) 15 to 30 – non-autistic; (2) 30 to 37 – mild to moderate autism; (3) 37 to 60 – severe autism.

In our sample, the average scores for ADOS 2 and CARS 2 were 20.3 (SD = 0.40) and 42 (SD = 5.00), respectively. Exclusion criteria included: (a) participation in behavioral qualification/rehabilitation treatments; (b) sensory disturbances (e.g., hearing or vision impairments); and (c) severe neurological disorders (e.g., drug-resistant epilepsy, cerebral palsy, neuromuscular diseases).

All enrolled children received psychomotor treatment for six months, with evaluations conducted at baseline (T0 – before starting treatment) and at the end of the observation period (T1 – after treatment). Treatment was provided by trained child therapists in outpatient settings, two to five times a week. Each therapist followed a standardized protocol, maintaining continuity by working with the same child throughout the six months. Standard sessions lasted 45 minutes.

Therapists used the ASDBI scale (the Uzbek version of the Pervasive Developmental Disorder Behavior Inventory (PDDBI)) at baseline (T0) and after six months (T1) to assess changes in the child's behavior over the study period.

Results.

The average age of participants was 57.2 ± 16.1 months. Of the 60 patients, 45 were male (75%), and 35 were verbal (58%). Psychomotor therapy sessions ranged from two to five times per week, averaging 3.5 ± 0.6 hours weekly.

According to DSM-5 recommendations, participants were categorized into three levels based on symptom severity. Level 1 (10%) included six children (4 boys), Level 2 (33.3%) included 20 children (15 boys), and Level 3 (56.7%) included 34 children (26 boys).

At baseline (T0), CARS2 scores were distributed as follows: severe ASD symptoms (>37): 42; moderate symptoms (30–36.5): 17; minimal signs or no symptoms (15–29.5): 1. After six months (T1), CARS2 scores showed: severe ASD symptoms (>37): 35; moderate symptoms (30–36.5): 24; minimal signs or no symptoms (15–29.5): 1.

After six months of psychomotor treatment, significant reductions were observed in domains such as excitability (ECCIT), aggression (AGG), social relations (RELSOC), expressiveness (all $p < 0.001$), sensory/perceptual contact (SENS) ($p = 0.0007$), ritualism/resistance to changes (RIT) ($p = 0.0002$), pragmatic/social issues (PPSOC) ($p = 0.0009$), specific fears (FEARS) ($p = 0.01$), and learning and memory (AMLR) ($p = 0.0007$).

Discussion.

This study is the first to explore the impact of six months of psychomotor treatment in children with ASD, showing significant improvements in areas most affected by the disorder, particularly in social communication, reciprocal interaction, and functional and symbolic play.

Psychomotor therapy has been proposed as an effective therapeutic option for various neuropsychiatric disorders, including separation anxiety, selective mutism, maltreatment, elimination disorders, and physical abuse. Widely used in some European countries, such as Italy and France, this approach emphasizes body experience as a core element in personal identity development, emotional expression, and cognitive evolution. Working with the body helps children experience self-unity in a kinesthetic and sensory space, enabling them to overcome emotional and physical hesitations.

ASD is marked by rigid and repetitive behaviors that provide individuals with a sense of security in what they perceive as a chaotic environment. Impaired motor skills have been identified as an early sign of ASD. Previous research has highlighted the value of psychomotor assessment in identifying ASD early and enhancing understanding of developmental patterns.

The psychomotor approach gradually integrates into a child's rituals, modifying behavior across all contexts of their life and reinforcing alternative, positive behaviors. This intervention supports the development of social interaction skills through role-playing and social narratives, which can help children with ASD improve social understanding. The approach also addresses environmental strategies, such as identifying and mitigating sensory hypersensitivity, which could cause increased arousal. Therapists work on emotional regulation not by instructing children on emotional control but by providing empathetic support that helps them manage their emotional experiences.

Aggressive behavior is more common in children with ASD compared to typically developing peers, often leading to negative social outcomes. Addressing aggression is crucial to improving outcomes for children with ASD and their caregivers. Our findings suggest significant improvements in specific traits (e.g., ECCIT, AGG, RELSOC, SENS, RIT, PPSOC, FEARS, and AMLR domains) after six months of psychomotor treatment, except in the language domain (including PPSEM and LESP), which may require a more specific and longer-term approach.

Conclusions.

ASD is a complex neurodevelopmental disorder primarily characterized by social dysfunction, affecting both the emotional and cognitive dimensions of individuals, often creating substantial burdens for parents. Behavioral therapies are recommended for managing ASD. In this context, psychomotor therapy stands out as a non-intrusive, relatively affordable, and adaptable option suitable for both clinical and home settings, and for groups or individual sessions. This approach is particularly tailored for children, offering high adaptability that aligns well with the unique features of the disorder.

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